

The synthesis of aryl cyanamides through C-N cross-coupling

Lakshmi Kondraganti^a, Surendra Babu Manabolu^{*b} and Rama Chandran Dittakavi^c

^aJawaharlal Nehru Technological University Kakinada, Kakinada-533 003, Andhra Pradesh, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, GITAM School of Technology, GITAM University, HTP Campus, Rudraram, Medak-502 329, Telangana, India

E-mail: manabolu@gmail.com

^cDepartment of Chemistry, Acharya Nagarjuna University, Nagarjuna Nagar-522 510, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India

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The methodology for the preparation of aromatic cyanamides has been demonstrated. The present method involves consecutive desulphurization/C-N cross-coupling reaction. Cheap, readily available and air stable cobalt catalyst has been used for this methodology. In addition, the substrate scope has been explored.

Keywords: Aromatic cyanamides, cobalt catalyst, C-N cross-coupling reaction, consecutive reaction, desulphurization.

Introduction

In synthetic organic chemistry, cyanamide is an important functional group because of its unique reactivity. It is a good intermediate for the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds that have biologically, medicinally and pharmaceutical importance¹⁻¹². Cyano functional group is easy removal group from cyanamides¹³, therefore, it generally acts as useful protecting group for the synthesis of secondary and tertiary amines containing heterocycles¹⁻¹⁶. In addition, cyanamides display apparent tumor growth inhibition activity^{17,18}. Apart from that many researchers have developed several reagents from cyanamides¹⁹⁻²³.

The preparation of cyanamides is achieved by traditional method from the reaction of gaseous cyanogen chloride or cyanogen bromide with amines or with imide salts²⁴. The most frequently appropriate method for the synthesis of cyanamides is the cyanation of amine using cyanogen halides, or synthon (CN⁺)^{25,26}. In an alternative approach, cyanamides are obtained from ureas, thioureas²⁷⁻³⁰ and amidoximes³¹. Recently, they were prepared from organic isocyanides and trimethylsilyl azide via Si-N bond cleavage catalyzed by $[(\eta^3\text{-C}_3\text{H}_5)\text{PdCl}]_2$ ³² and in one pot by reacting isocyanate or isothiocyanate with sodium bis(trimethylsilyl)amide as deoxygenating or desulfurizing agent in the presence of THF at room temperature^{33,34}. Cyanamides were prepared from *N*,

N-disubstituted glycyamide using a pentavalent iodine reagent in the presence of tetraethyl ammonium bromide at ambient temperature³⁵. Recently, Patel and co-authors reported for the synthesis of cyanamides from thiocarbamate salts³⁶ using hypervalent iodine(III) reagent and Yeh *et al.* demonstrated preparation of cyanamides from amines using sodium bis(trimethylsilyl)amide reagent³⁷. Most of the reports have used cyano cation (CN⁺), which gets from toxic cyanogen halides, strong alkaline conditions, toxic and expensive reagents, high reaction temperature. Other researchers have reported at high temperature, giving low yields and involving tedious purification procedures. To overcome the above referred disadvantages, the efficient method is needed. In this connection, here in we wish to report high yielding one pot synthesis of cyanamides from thiourea via consecutive desulfurization³⁸⁻⁴³/C-N cross-coupling reaction⁴⁴⁻⁵² using cheap, readily available and air stable cobalt source as catalyst under mild reaction conditions.

Experimental materials and methods

Physical measurements:

Thiourea, aniline, CS₂, CoCl₂.6H₂O, CoSO₄.H₂O, Co(NO₃)₂.6H₂O, Et₃N, pyridine, sodium bicarbonate, K₃PO₄.3H₂O, KOH, K₂CO₃, Cs₂CO₃ were purchased from Aldrich and used without further purification. The solvents were purchased and dried according to standard procedure

prior to use. ^1H NMR (400 MHz) spectra were recorded with a Varian 400 spectrometer. Infrared (IR) spectra recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrum one FT-IR spectrometer. VKSI Medico Centrifuge machine was used for our experimental procedure for the synthesis of substituted cyanamides. Iodo benzenes have been prepared using the reported procedure.

General procedure for construction of phenylcyanamide:

To a stirred solution of DMSO solvent (2–3 ml), thiourea (1 mmol, 76 mg) was added in slowly and followed by Et_3N (1 mmol, 101 mg) and $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (50 mol%, 125 mg) were added at room temperature. The whole reaction mixture stirred for one hour (until get the black color) at room temperature. The reaction was monitored by TLC. After finish the reaction (according to TLC), to this, iodobenzene (1 mmol, 204 mg), Cs_2CO_3 (1 mmol, 325 mg), $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (10 mol%, 24 mg) and 1,10-phenanthroline (20 mol%, 36 mg) were added consecutively in slowly for several and the reaction mixture was stirred for 12 h at 115°C . The progress of the reaction was investigated by TLC (5% ethylacetate in hexane). After finish the reaction, the reaction mixture was transferred into centrifuged tubes and the mixture was centrifuged for 10 min by using centrifugation machine. Black color solid was settled in the bottom of centrifuged tubes. The clear solution was concentrated by using rotary evaporator and the crude mixture was purified by silica gel (60–120 mesh) column chromatography using 5% ethylacetate in hexane as eluent to obtain a phenyl cyanamide as a white solid.

Phenylcyanamide: Analytical TLC on silica gel, 1:19 ethyl acetate/hexane $R_f = 0.8$; yield 90%; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 7.37–7.33 (2H, m), 7.29–7.25 (3H, m), 5.81 (1H, br. s, NH); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 137.8, 130.6, 130.1, 128.9, 114.3; FT-IR (KBr): 3350, 3064, 2222, 1693, 1489, 1250, 1070, 909 cm^{-1} . Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_2$: C, 71.17; H, 5.12; N, 23.71. Found: C, 71.28; H, 5.09; N, 23.62.

Results and discussion

Thiourea gave cyanamide, which is confirmed by IR analysis ($-\text{CN}-$ 2222 cm^{-1}) via desulphurization process using cobalt source as catalyst. It reacts with iodobenzene using cobalt source as catalyst under moderate reaction conditions to afford the target product as phenyl cyanamide (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Pathway for the synthesis of aromatic cyanamides.

Firstly, the optimization of the 1st step reaction conditions was performed using the readily available thiourea as model substrate with different cobalt sources and solvents at room temperature (Table 1). We were pleased to observe that the substrate proceeded reaction with 1 equiv. Et_3N and 50 mol% cobalt source in the presence of EtOH, EtOAc, DMSO and DMF at room temperature to afford the corresponding unsubstituted cyanamide in complete conversion. The reaction using non polar solvents like *n*-hexane and *n*-heptane didn't give unsubstituted cyanamide (Table 1, entries 3-4). Control experiment confirmed that the reaction didn't proceed in the absence of cobalt source (Table 1, entry 15).

Table 1. Optimization for the synthesis of unsubstituted cyanamides^a

Entry	Solvent, Et_3N (1 eq) Cobalt source (1 eq)		Conversion A (%)
	Solvent	Cobalt source	
1.	EtOH	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	100
2.	EtOAc	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	100
3.	<i>n</i> -Hexane	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	n.d.
4.	<i>n</i> -Heptane	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	n.d.
5.	H_2O	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	50
6.	DMF	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	100
7.	DMSO	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	100
8.	DMSO	$\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	100
9.	DMSO	$\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	100
10 ^b .	DMSO	$\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	100
11 ^c .	DMSO	$\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	62
12.	DMSO	–	n.d.

^aReaction conditions: Thiourea (1 mmol), solvent (2 mL), Et_3N (1 equiv.), cobalt source (1 equiv.), 1 h, room temperature. ^bCobalt source (50 mol%) was used. ^cCobalt source (25 mol%) was used. n.d. = not detected.

Soon after finish the 1st step optimization, we could focus on the standardization of 2nd step. In this regard, thiourea could provide unsubstituted cyanamide, that, gratifyingly, proceeded an intermolecular *N*-arylation with iodobenzene using 10 mol% cobalt source, 20 mol% ligand

(1,10-phenanthroline) and 1 equiv. Cs_2CO_3 at 115°C temperature to give target product in complete conversion in the presence of DMSO (Table 2, entry 7). The reaction using Cs_2CO_3 exhibited greater reactivity compared to that of $\text{K}_3\text{PO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, K_2CO_3 and KOH . In a set of ligands **L1-L3** screened, **L3** was found to be the most effective in comparison to **L1-L2** (Table 2, entries 8-9). Cobalt sources ($\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) exhibited a similar catalytic activity (Table 2, entries 7 and 10-11 and 13-14). Lowering the amount of base (1 equiv.) or the cobalt source (5 mol%) led to the *N*-arylation to afford target product in less conversion (Table 2, entries 15-16). Control experiments without the cobalt source and ligand confirmed that the formation of final product was not observed (Table 2, entry 18).

Having the optimal conditions in hand, the scope of the

protocol was next explored to substituted cyanamides (Table 3). The process was general and a series of aryl iodides to give the corresponding aromatic cyanamides **2a-k** in moderate to good yield. The substrates having both electron donating and electron withdrawing substituents on the aryl rings could give their respective target product in moderate to high yield. Aryl iodide having electron donating substituents (4-Me, 2-Me, 4-OMe and 2,4-dimethyl) exhibited greater reactivity compared to that bearing electron withdrawing substituent's (4-Cl, 4-F, 4-CN and 4-COOMe groups). The phenyl ring having electron donating groups such as 4-methoxy, 4-methyl could give their respective aromatic cyanamides (Table 3, entries 2-3) in 95% yield. The unsubstituted phenyl ring also gave target product in excellent yield (Table 2, entry 1). Electron withdrawing groups such as 4-chloro and 4-fluoro substituents gave their target pro-

Table 2. Optimization for the synthesis of aromatic cyanamides^a

Entry	Solvent	Cobalt source	Base	Ligand	Conversion ^b	
					A	2a
1.	EtOH	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{K}_3\text{PO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	L3	100	n.d.
2.	EtOAc	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{K}_3\text{PO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	L3	100	n.d.
3.	DMF	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{K}_3\text{PO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	L3	25	75
4.	DMSO	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{K}_3\text{PO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	L3	25	75
5.	DMSO	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	KOH	L3	20	80
6.	DMSO	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	K_2CO_3	L3	40	60
7.	DMSO	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Cs_2CO_3	L3	n.d.	100
8.	DMSO	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Cs_2CO_3	L1	75	25
9.	DMSO	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Cs_2CO_3	L2	64	36
10.	DMSO	$\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	Cs_2CO_3	L3	n.d.	100
11.	DMSO	$\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Cs_2CO_3	L3	n.d.	100
12 ^c .	DMSO	2O	Cs_2CO_3	L3	40	60
13 ^d .	DMSO	$\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	Cs_2CO_3	L3	50	50
14.	DMSO	$\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	Cs_2CO_3	–	87	13
15.	DMSO	$\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	Cs_2CO_3	–	100	n.d.

^aReaction conditions: Thiourea (1 mmol), solvent (2 mL), Et_3N (1 equiv.), $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (50 mol%), 1 h, room temperature, then, catalyst (10 mol%), ligand (20 mol%), base (1 mmol), 18 h, 115°C . ^bConversion was confirmed crude ^1H NMR. ^cCobalt source (5 mol%) used. ^d Cs_2CO_3 (0.5 equiv.) used. n.d. = not detected.

Table 3. Substrate scope for the synthesis of aromatic cyanamides^a

Entry	Substrate	Product	Yield ^b
1.	(2a)	98	
2.	(2b)	98	
3.	(2c)	95	
4.	(2d)	82	
5.	(2e)	79	
6.	(2f)	45	
7.	(2g)	43	
8.	(2h)	60	
9.	(2i)	82	
10.	(2j)	93	
11.	(2k)	85	

^aReaction conditions: Thiourea (1 mmol), DMSO (2 mL), Et₃N (1 equiv.), CoSO₄·H₂O (50 mol %), 1 h, room temperature, then, CoSO₄·H₂O (10 mol %), ligand (20 mol %), base (1 mmol), 18 h, 115 °C. ^bIsolated yield.

ducts in 82% and 79% yields, respectively (Table 2, entries 4 and 5). Aryl ring bearing other strong electron withdrawing

substituent's nitrile, ester and nitro could give target products (Table 2, entries 6-8) in moderate yield. *Ortho* and *meta* substituted methyl groups on aryl ring could give their respective target products in 82–93% yields (Table 1, entries 9 and 10). Di-methyl substituent on aryl ring gave final product in 80% yield (Table 2, entry 11).

Finally, the click chemistry of aryl cyanamides was studied with aryl azides that can afford a straight forward route for the construction of substituted *N*,1-diaryl-1*H*-tetrazol-5-amine (Scheme 2). Optimized studies revealed that the reactions are effective under the below shown reaction conditions³¹. For examples, the click reactions of a few aromatic cyanamides **2a**, **2b**, **2d**, **2e**, **2h** and **2k** were studied with aryl azides. The reactions proceeded readily to afford the respective *N*,1-diaryl-1*H*-tetrazol-5-amines **A-F** in moderate to high yields.

Scheme 2. Synthesis of phenyl tetrazolamine.

The mechanism of formation for aromatic cyanamides from thiourea is shown in Scheme 3. The experimental evidence and from the literature reports the mechanism is proposed. Cobalt can co-ordinate with thiourea and followed by removal of protons to afford intermediate **R** via intermediates **P** and **Q**. The intermediate **R** may provide unsubstituted cyanamide along with byproduct CoS and poly sulphide⁵³ via desulphurization⁵⁴. On the other hand, oxidative addition of aryl iodide with cobalt complex can lead to the formation of **a** which can undergo intermolecular C-N cross-coupling reaction⁵⁵ with unsubstituted cyanamide using base to give the intermediate **b** that can complete the catalytic cycle by

Scheme 3. Proposed mechanism.

reductive elimination to get target product aromatic cyanamides. In addition, the atomic absorption of the aqueous solution active cobalt salt, $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ was measured to reveal the presence trace of copper which was observed in the iron-catalyzed⁵⁶ cross-coupling as the active catalyst. However, the present protocol, no trace of copper was detected with the detection limit of 1 ppm. This experiment clearly suggests that copper has not involved in the present methodology.

Conclusions

In conclusion, we have developed methodology for the synthesis of aromatic cyanamides from thiourea using cheap, readily available and air stable cobalt source as catalyst under moderate reaction conditions. The reactions were involved desulfurization followed by C-N cross-coupling reaction. All the substrates could obtain their target products in good to excellent yields.

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